

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON ROAD TRANSPORTATION

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The transportation sector is tremendously important to people's daily lives. Everyone must move from one location to the next one that is necessary. Without transportation-related policies in place, a society cannot operate at its best. We employ a variety of forms of transportation to move things between locations in addition to moving people. Transportation of all kinds contributes to India's economic prosperity, but the COVID epidemic requires lockdown throughout the country. Everyone was experiencing great difficulty at the time, and the government was unable to act quickly enough to stop the pandemic. Additionally, the profitability, influx and outflow of finances, operational and non-operating income, number of people to travel, etc. have all been negatively impacted by the Karnataka State Road Transportation Corporation. The COVID epidemic has had a significant influence on a number of sectors, including the transportation industry. The epidemic has had a tremendous impact on the public and private sectors.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The State of Karnataka's public transport corporation's inter- and intra-city operations have undergone thorough operational and financial analysis. to assess the effectiveness of public transportation operations at various levels, including corporations' divisions, depots, and routes in Karnataka, using both quantitative and qualitative data. Alternative depot locations have been found in order to cut down on dead kilometres, which will result in significant financial savings for the company.*

Findings/Results: *The main of this paper is to identify challenges faced and remedies which are taken by KSRTC of Dakshina Kannada while lockdown period. The secondary source of information has taken for the study and used some statistics tools applied to analysis of data.*

Originality/Value: *The study helps to identify the impact of Covid-19 on the performance of bus transportation of Dakshine Kannada.*

Paper Type: *Conceptual Research.*

Keywords: *Impact of Covid-19 on transportation, Challenges faced and remedies taken by the KSRTC impost Covid-19, Problems faced by the passengers during this pandemic*

1. INTRODUCTION :

The (2019/2020-COVID-19) new virus outbreak has caused an increase in infections, fatalities, and recoveries across the globe. Although pandemics are different from previous disasters in nature, a delay in the recovery process could have a significant negative impact on the general public and industry. The estimated total number of illnesses and deaths as of October 2nd was 43,952,991 and 1,166,886 correspondingly. Many nations quickly adopted strict measures to limit the sickness after this. The actions made have brought about a financial crisis. Globally, there were 517330 fatalities and 10,719,648 cases as of July 2, 2020. By October, there were more than a million confirmed cases, and the number was growing quickly. Numerous changes in the social, economic, and environmental spheres were a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. This essay's goal is to examine COVID-19's effects on the system of road transportation. The transportation sector is tremendously important to people's daily lives. Everyone must move from one location to the next one that is necessary. Transportation of all kinds contributes to India's economic progress, but the COVID pandemic has forced the country into lockdown. Everyone was experiencing great difficulty at the time, and the government was unable to act quickly enough to stop the pandemic. Additionally, the profitability, influx and outflow of finances, operational and non-operating income, and number of people to be transported, etc. have all suffered due to the Karnataka State Road Transportation Corporation. The COVID epidemic has had a significant influence on a number of sectors, including the transportation industry. The epidemic has had a tremendous impact on the public and private sectors. The Covid-19 pandemic has a particularly negative impact on the road transportation, airline industry, railroads, and energy sector, which supplies fuel to all of them. The nations that experience a significant impact have shifted from China to European nations and then to the USA. Also, more recently, the virus has struck nations like India, Brazil, and Russia. After the pandemic, most nations began to take steps to restrict international travel. In the majority of the main cities, public transportation has undergone significant change. Around the world, 50–90% fewer people use the subway and buses. It is a difficult challenge to provide enough capacity and guarantee the safety of passengers who rely on the metro, buses, trams, and light rails when the cities are released from quarantines and lockdowns. The global transportation industry has taken a variety of actions in response to the current pandemic. Few automakers have ceased making cars in favour of producing respirators and ventilators, as well as free transportation services for medical staff and the delivery of food to displaced residents by taxis and ride-sharing services. Aircraft crew will also provide support to medical personnel and receive first-responder training.

2. RELEVANT LITERATURE :

The current study will look at how the COVID-19 epidemic has affected employment in the transportation sector. In order to do this, we rely on two bodies of related research, which help us define our model and explain the findings in the following sections of the paper. Work on the pandemic's effects on employment first. Two, the COVID-19 project has an effect on how people move about, how many people use public transportation, and how social equity affects both industry employees and customers.

2.1 EMPLOYMENT IMPACTS OF COVID-19 :

According to an assessment of the economics of COVID-19 research, the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) had published 160 working papers on the subject by the end of June 2020. (Brodeur et al., 2020). The analysis of how many and what kinds of workers were impacted by the epidemic takes up a significant portion of this effort.

According to one assessment of the effects of the epidemic on employment in the first few months (April and May), many of the jobs that were lost required frequent human interaction and could not be performed remotely (Montenovo et al., 2020). The same study discovered that demographic factors such as gender, race, and age were statistically significant explanatory factors of unemployment caused by the epidemic even after accounting for job sorting, or how market forces partition people into positions. In particular, model results show that employees who are younger, Blacks, Hispanics, and single parents (who are largely female) have been disproportionately affected by pandemic-related job losses (Montenovo et al., 2020).

According to related study, employees who belong to racial/ethnic minorities, particularly African Americans and Latinx workers had the biggest increases in unemployment during the pandemic's early months (Fairlie et al., 2020). Latinx employees within these two groups saw the biggest increases in unemployment due of their concentration in specific industries. The overrepresentation in the pandemic-affected industries (such as leisure and hospitality, wholesale and retail trade, construction, and services) and underrepresentation in the pandemic-affected industries is likely what accounts for the higher unemployment rates among Latinx workers (e.g., Management, Business, and Financial Occupations, Professional and Related Occupations).

2.2 COVID-19 IMPACTS ON THE TRANSPORTATION INDUSTRY :

Three areas are the focus of the transportation-related study on COVID-19 effects: trends in mobility use of various modes of transportation, and equitable effects of changes in transportation. Numerous studies have examined how people moved about during the pandemic. Arellana et al. (2020) examined the short-term effects of the pandemic on aviation, freight, and urban transport in a study conducted in Colombia. They discovered that government regulations, such as a restriction on air travel, had a negative impact on mobility, transit use, and congestion. Using survey data gathered in the early months of the epidemic, Riggs and Appleyard (2020) examined changes in travel behaviour brought on by telework during the pandemic in the U.S. (March and April of 2020). It's interesting to note that telework was a major contributor to the rise in recreational foot and bike excursions (i.e., additional trips generated while working from home).

3. OBJECTIVES :

The purpose of the article is to analyse the current situation and specifically find the answers to the following questions:

- The major goal of this essay is to outline the difficulties encountered and actions performed by KSRTC of Dakshina Kannada during the shutdown time. The study's secondary source of data was utilised, and various statistics methods were applied to the data analysis. Originality/Value: The study aids in determining the effect of COVID-19 on the efficiency of Dakshina Kannada bus transit.
- What are the three environmental challenges that the epidemic has brought to light? How can transportation be crucial to solving these problems?
- Do stakeholders and the public still value transportation innovations and technical breakthroughs the same way they did before the pandemic?
- How can we use the sustainability framework to make decisions about how to finance transportation foundations so that we don't have to compromise on the economy, the environment, or our social prosperity?

4. METHODOLOGY :

The study uses quantitative approach and is empirical in character. It is based on data regarding the impact of the corona virus on the Transport Corporation. Data has been gathered for the study's purposes from secondary sources. Regarding the impact of COVID-19, secondary data are taken from KSRTC official reports, a number of periodicals, and the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. By using statistical methods like tabulation, percentile, and other techniques, the data were measured, assessed, and analysed. The major goal of this essay is to outline the difficulties encountered and actions performed by KSRTC of Dakshina Kannada during the shutdown time. The study's secondary source of data was utilised, and various statistics methods were applied to the data analysis. The main goals of this study were to provide a thorough evaluation of the literature on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on road transportation systems by taking into account the following.

- COVID-19.
- Pandemic.
- Public road transportation and physical distancing

5. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY :

In its 56th year of operation, the Karnataka State Road Transport Corporation (KSRTC) tops all other State road transport companies in India. KSRTC has pioneered and achieved success in a variety of fields over the years, including the use of information technology, open HR practises, environmental initiatives, etc. With 209 Awards won by the STU to date, including the Information Technology Award National E-Governance 2016-17 Gold Award, the Award of Excellence by the Ministry of Urban Development, and the International Public Transport Award, these initiatives were well recognised in numerous national and international forums (UITP). In our bus stops, they intend to set up public mineral water drinking fountains for the very reasonable price of one rupee per litre. Reverse osmosis will be used to purify the water, and a coin-operated vending system will be used to make it available. Bus uses solar power that it generates on its own. A wash basin and solar sensor lights are also included. When providing basic amenities to female passengers at bus stops, the firm feels that hygiene should be a primary priority. KSRTC maintains well-equipped bus terminals with cutting-edge infrastructure. With well-designed seating arrangements, reservation counters, digital displays, intelligent transport systems, public address systems, tourist information kiosks, crew restrooms, cloakrooms, drinking water and canteen facilities, commercial establishments and offices, modern toilets, two-wheeler and four-wheeler parking facilities, ATM centres, and pre-paid taxi and auto-rickshaw stands, the modern, high-tech bus stations had all transportation amenities and services under one roof. Some bus stations have recently started offering free Wi-Fi services.

6. OVERVIEW :

The current state of the transportation industry is completely unprecedented. It is likely the main facilitator of social interaction when it comes to enabling citizens to interact face-to-face as one of its primary tasks in society. Due to the limitations put in place globally, that function has now been suspended. It must also continue to operate in areas where transferring people and products is required, not optional. It's important for nurses and doctors to be able to commute. Hospitals must have access to the supplies they require. Citizens who are confined rely on food deliveries to stores. Last but not least, to minimise the inevitable economic damage, global supply networks must continue to operate as effortlessly as feasible. The transportation industry as a whole is handling the Coronavirus issue with empathy and innovation. Respirator production is being shifted by automakers. High-speed trains are being converted into mobile hospitals by rail companies. First-responder-trained

grounded aeroplane cabin employees are assisting medical personnel. Taxis and ride-sharing services provide patients and medical personnel with free transportation or bring food to disadvantaged individuals. There are a tonne more instances. Some analysts have highlighted the advantages of the unheard-of decline in transportation activity. In many areas, air pollution has significantly decreased.

According to ITF predictions, transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions will likely be 20% lower in 2020 than they would be under typical conditions. Because there are fewer cars on the roads, there will probably be fewer traffic fatalities. In many locations, cycling has gained popularity as a risk-free, healthful substitute for public transportation. Nearly every area of transportation in the US has undergone significant modifications and disruptions as a result of the new coronavirus Sars-Cov-2, also known as COVID-19. The virus itself, orders to stay at home, and even social estrangement have all had a significant negative impact on the aviation, automotive, and rail sectors as well as the energy corporations that sustain them all. The transportation sector is being forced to change its focus from moving people and products across the nation to maintaining a core transportation system with a smaller staff as demand for travel falls to a modern all-time low. Maintaining the nation's transportation network ensures that workers and cargo can continue to travel. A rapid change in their revenue sources is forcing many transportation businesses to make these necessary operational adjustments, which is causing them to run into financial difficulties.

7. PASSENGER AMENITIES AND FACILITIES :

The Corporation has accorded high priority to provide increased amenities to the travelling public. As on 31-03-2019, there were 166 permanent bus stations. The long distance expresses non-stop and Premier A/C and non A/C services were further augmented to meet the needs of the travelling public. In order to provide more comfort to the traveling public, 20 Leyland Karnataka Sarige (NAL Fully built), 243 Leyland Karnataka Sarige (NAL), 11 Leyland Gramina Sarige BS-4, 51 Eicher Karnataka Sarige(NAL BS-4), 20 Leyland Non A/C sleeper fully built, 16 Eicher fully built Rajahamsa, 24 Volvo Multi axle and 06 Volvo Multi axle Fly bus, totalling 391 new buses were inducted during the year 2018-19. As on 31-03-2019, in all 1421 long distance routes were in operation with route length ranging from 120 Kms. to 1048 Kms. The Corporation operated 2884 ordinary, 3763 express, 1 semi-deluxe, 197 Rajahamsa, 22 Karnataka Vaibhav, 108 Non A/C Sleeper, 60 A/C sleeper, 103 Airavat (Volvo), 07 Airavat (Benz), 279 Airavat Club class (Multi axle Volvo 204, Multi axle Scania 58, Multi axle Mercedes 17), 15 Fly bus, 45 Volvo (City), 630 City and 105 Suburban services as on 31-03-2019.

8. IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON OPERATIONS :

- Due to the Covid-19 Lockdown and related restrictions, operations were hampered. In March 2020, KSRTC ran 8172 schedules. According to the order from the governments of India and Karnataka, complete lockdown because of COVID-19 was imposed starting on March 2, 2020, and as a result, the Corporation's whole traffic operation was suspended for 43 days.
- Stranded migrant workers inside the state were given free transportation, and workers from other states were given free transit to the closest train station.
- According to orders from the governments of India and Karnataka, activities began in the green zone districts on May 4, 2020, and on May 19, 2020, operations began throughout the entire state from dawn to dusk at 7:00 p.m. Then, starting on June 1, 2020, the operating hours were changed from morning 5:00 to evening 9:00.
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throughout the entire state from dawn to dusk at 7:00 p.m. Then, starting on June 1, 2020, the operating hours were changed from morning 5:00 to evening 9:00.

- Transport services were made available from one district to another. District/Taluka to State Capital, Taluka to Taluka, and Villages to Taluka. All regular and municipal services were being restored as needed.
- Despite the fact that the operation of A/C buses was restored in its entirety on June 25, 2020, the demand for A/C buses had drastically decreased.
- KSRTC Bus services were only permitted to run with 50% of the bus's seating capacity until August 31, 2021.
- There was no addition of new schedules throughout the year.
- The full cost was paid to all travellers who reserved seats in advance through counters or online for travel from 20-03-2020 to 28-05-2020 without subtracting any cancellation fees.
- Interstate operations started on June 17, 2020 for Andhra Pradesh, on August 24, 2020 for Kerala, on September 7, 2020 for Goa, on September 22, 2020 for Maharashtra, on September 29, 2020 for Telangana, on October 23, 2020 for Puducherry, and on November 11, 2020 for Tamil Nadu state.
- Low passenger turnout to tourist locations and low passenger density in bus stations. Employees at businesses and industries were permitted to work from home, and colleges and schools were closed. As a result, there wasn't much of a demand from travellers. As a result, KSRTC was unable to run all of the schedules as they were during the pre-covid time. However, more schedules were being added in response to the volume of traffic and the demand from passengers.

9. HYPOTHESIS :

H₀₁: (Null Hypothesis): there is no significant impact of Covid-19 on the transportation industry in Karnataka (I.e., KSRTC). (H₀₁: $\mu = \bar{x} = 0$).

H₁₁: (Alternative Hypothesis): there is significant impact of Covid-19 on the transportation industry in Karnataka. (H₀₁: $\mu \neq \bar{x} \neq 0$).

H₀₂: (Null Hypothesis): there is no significant challenges of Covid-19 impacted on the KSRTC (H₀₂: $\mu = \bar{x} = 0$).

H₁₂: (Alternative Hypothesis): there are many significant challenges of Covid-19 impacted on the transportation business such as KSRTC (H₀₂: $\mu \neq \bar{x} \neq 0$).

H₀₃: (Null Hypothesis): there is no remedies to overcome from the impact of Covid-19 on the transportation business in Karnataka (H₀₃: $\mu = \bar{x} = 0$).

H₁₃: (Alternative Hypothesis): there are many remedies to overcome from the impact of Covid-19 on the transportation business in Karnataka (H₁₃: $\mu \neq \bar{x} \neq 0$).

10. DATA ANALYSIS AND INFERENCE :

Although India's economy has been successfully growing over the past 20 years, a pandemic has recently occurred that is already having an impact and will continue to do so in the future. By 2020, the GDP growth rate will have decreased to around 3%. One of the most important elements in determining the impact of the corona virus is the population; as a result of growing population density, the corona virus's rate of dissemination has been rising steadily over time. This epidemic has greatly impacted the KSRTC as well, and this will be covered in more detail in the following section.

11. REVENUE LOSS TO THE KSRTC DUE TO LOCKDOWN :

The KSRTC reported significant income loss during the lockdown due to the corona virus. In order to maintain the attention of the travelling public and to stop the corona virus from spreading throughout the state, the transportation corporation has experienced income loss. KSRTC and numerous other private bus companies, taxis, cabs, delivery trucks, and auto rickshaws have spent thousands of dollars in costs, and 90% of the fleet has been forced to cease operations. Earlier, the KSRTC received an average of 22 to 23 thousand reservations per day; however, after the lockdown, that number fell to 12 to 13 thousand reservations per day, and on March 16 alone, the corporation had to cancel 585 buses due to a lack of customers.

Table 1: Shows revenue loss incurred from 1st to 18th March, 2020.

KSRTC has offering both premium and non-premium services to the public; most of the revenue arises to the KSRTC from premium services, from 1st to 15th March 2020.

Nature of Service	Revenue Loss (₹)	Percentage
Premium Service	5,33,82,456	62.15
Non-premium services	3,25,04,006	37.85
Total	8,58,86,462	100

KSRTC Reports and Business Newspaper is the source.

The KSRTC experienced revenue losses on both premium and non-premium services during the lockdown period, according to the table above. KSRTC suffered a loss of 1,90,25,183 on March 18. The COVID-19 has a significant impact on KSRTC's performance. The cancellation of luxury and premium services cost the company about 62.15% of its income, and termination of non-premium services cost the remaining 37.85%. It has been discovered that the KSRTC has increased its earnings by providing upscale and premium services.

Table 2: Shows corporation-wise revenue loss incurred during lockdown.

(Null Hypothesis): there is no significant impact of Covid-19 on the transportation industry in Karnataka.

(Alternative Hypothesis): there is significant impact of Covid-19 on the transportation industry in Karnataka.

Corporation	Revenue Loss (₹ in Crores)	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
KSRTC	314.89	38.58	38.58
NWKRTC	172.00	21.07	59.65
NEKRTC	180.00	22.05	81.70
BMTC	149.34	18.30	100.00
Total	816.23	100	-

KSRTC Reports and Business Newspaper is the source.

The above table shows how the corona virus affected KSRTC's revenue, with a total loss of \$816.23 crores occurring during the lockdown. From a total loss The majority of the loss was borne by KSRTC, 22.05% of the loss belonged to NWKRTC, while the remaining two divisions each experienced losses ranging from 18 to 22%.

The H0 was rejected, and as a result, the H1 was accepted, demonstrating that COVID-19 had a significant impact on KSRTC's regular operation due to the payment of fixed costs, which are not avoidable, and variable costs, which are avoidable by nature. However, due to the pandemic, KSRTC engaged in the free transportation of about 1, 18,982 migrant workers to their homes.

Table 3: Shows division-wise revenue-loss incurred during lockdown.

Due to the government's lockdown order to stop the spread of the corona virus, which affected all 17 divisions and 4 regional workshops operating within the State, most of the divisions suffered significant losses, some of which are briefly described in the table below.

Division	Revenue Loss (₹ in crores)	Percentage
Vijayapur	46.75	34.17
Managaluru	54.00	39.43
Puttur	32.00	23.37
Mysuru Rural	4.20	03.03
Total	136.95	100

Press release from KSRTC, Times of India.

According to the aforementioned table, 34% of the income loss suffered by the Vijayapur division, 39% by the Mangaluru division, 23% by the Puttur division, and 3% by the respondents were losses. As a result, the KSTDC has encountered various issues during this lockdown. Many in the transportation industry are currently experiencing a pandemic.

12. PRECAUTIONS TAKEN BY THE KSRTC :

- The Hon. Chief Minister of Karnataka officially opened the mobile fever clinic bus with Swab collecting in Mysuru, Mangalore, Hubballi, Belagavi, Raichur, Mandya, Tumkur, and Bagalkote.
- Every time the buses travelled, more safety measures were taken by the company, including thorough cleaning, sanitization, and disinfection.
- The Department of Health has provided the KSRTC personnel with a COVID-19 awareness programme. Free needed supplies are given to Pura Karmikas at the bus station, and both employees and passengers undergo thermal screening.
- KSRTC has made COVID awareness messages visible on bus tickets, caller tones, mask and sanitizer delivery, among other things.
- Transportation of migrant workers from various locations to their homes, free distribution of masks to passengers made at KSRTC workshops and depots.
- Corona virus containment using a mobile sanitising bus.
- Introduced a mobile fever clinic for Karnataka city police, and encouraged commuters to download the Arogya Setu app.
- The reduction of the Corona virus's propagation and the absence of penalties for cancelling tickets that had been pre-registered.

13. OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES TO THE KSRTC IN THE POST COVID-19. OPPORTUNITIES :

- Point-to-point service: This is advantageous for the organisation because customers are only boarded at designated stops and at predetermined times. As a result, it aids organisations in lowering costs and making hygienic maintenance possible.
- Private bus companies have chosen not to run: Private buses made the decision not to run during the outbreak. As a result, it represented KSRTC's greatest opportunity to increase passenger numbers and profitability.
- Allowing passengers to board at bus stops saves money and shortens wait times for the organisation.
- Air-conditioned bus use is prohibited: Covid-19 did not benefit from the use of air-conditioned buses. AC buses are not authorised to run because of COVID-19.
- KSRTC safeguards the security and well-being of its clients by: The KSRTC's top priority was the health and safety of its customers.
- In order to reduce the spread of the virus to customers and employees, KSRTC implemented a lockdown for several days during the Covid-19 period and offered the barest of services.
- For the sake of their employees' health, KSTDC has issued holidays to all of its workers.

14. CHALLENGES :

- The lockout had a detrimental impact on KSRTC's ability to generate money and made it challenging to pay employees' salaries during the pandemic.
- The government has declared that the bus crew will receive \$30 lakh in insurance during this period of financial hardship for the company. As a result, the KSRTC faced challenging circumstances.
- Operating costs increased after the lockout, and the State Government was forced to restrict bus seating to 50%, making it impossible to finance even the most basic maintenance costs.
- This is another significant issue that the KSRTC is dealing with: there were no buses in the containment zones. The lack of buses in the exclusion zones made it extremely difficult for residents to connect with other modes of transportation.

15. REMEDIES TO OVERCOME FROM THE CHALLENGES POSED BY COVID-19. :

- Restore public trust in safe public transportation by strictly enforcing hygiene and physical separation policies among KSRTC passengers.
- Create fiscal tools and a reform-based fiscal package to aid in the revitalization of transit networks and ease the financial load on bus-based systems.
- Implement long-term initiatives to improve integrated public transportation and services in the state of Karnataka.
- Give buses access to more protected lanes to increase fleet utilisation and carrying capacity.
- The introduction of work-from-home options for select employees.
- New seating and transport arrangements for people with social distance.

- A timeline of employees and bus service across all KSRTC divisions in Karnataka.

16. FINDINGS :

The analysis discovered that the COVID 19 pandemic was to blame for 62.15% of losses from premium services in just 18 days. 37.85% of losses were brought on by free services. This makes it likely that the KSRTC will suffer significant losses as a result of the pandemic.

- The investigation shows that all four firms collectively suffered losses of 816.23 crores. KSRTC suffered the highest losses, or 38.58%, while BMTC suffered the lowest losses, or 18.30%.
- To stop the spread and save lives during the COVID era, KSRTC took a number of initiatives and precautions. Mobile fever clinics, bus sanitization programmes, staff awareness campaigns, and the posting of COVID awareness messaging on buses are a few of the initiatives and safety measures.
- KSRTC discontinued operating AC buses during the COVID-19 period. It is better from an organisational standpoint and could lower operating costs.
- KSRTC made sure that passengers were well-cared for during their travels and that their safety came first.
- The analysis discovered that KSRTC's operating costs were higher during the period following the lockdown. As a result, the state government ordered that seats be cut to 50% on buses, which made it impossible to fund the necessary maintenance costs.

17. CONCLUSION :

The Indian transportation industry, in particular KSRTC, has been suffering significant losses as a result of both their operations and the COVID-19 pandemic. To overcome the difficulties the KSRTC and other Indian transport operators are facing, the transportation sector must take the appropriate steps and employ preventative measures. According to the shifting conditions in the transportation sector, people's lifestyles change. The development of the transportation industry depends heavily on the business models, modes of operation, laws and regulations, safety precautions, and other factors. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the entire country was paralysed, and every sector's growth and development were stunted. As a result, the KSRTC also participated in the transportation sector and suffered significant losses. That, taking care of people, making up safety precautions, and other things is the weapon to return. Large operating expenses were incurred by KSRTC during the COVID-19 epidemic. Finally, it must be stated that the competition from the private sector has put public sector transportation companies in a very difficult position. This is one cause, and another is extremely typical—the impact of environmental variables and the pandemic—both of which led to severe financial difficulties for KSRTC.

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